

Open - from local CRIS'es to global indexes and back: Creating a high-integrity national open research information and analytics platform in international collaboration

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Abstract

Research Portal Denmark (<https://forskningsportal.dk/>) is a national research information and analytics infrastructure and portal. It is based on data and expertise from institutional, national and global domains – collected, aligned, and interlinked in the infrastructure and the Open Access portal. The scope of coverage is Danish research outputs since 2011. With the advent of the global developments towards Open Research Information (<https://barcelona-declaration.org/>), the launch of OpenAlex and the CWTS Leiden Ranking Open Edition (<https://open.leidenranking.com/>), new opportunities have arisen to further develop the portal's degree of openness and analytical integrity. The presentation gives a step-by-step overview of the approaches taken and results achieved so far.

Danish research institutions

Danish research institutions document their research output in so called CRIS-systems. Researchers and librarians collaborate to achieve good coverage and compliance with the national Open Access policy. A national exchange format (XML schema) for this kind of metadata has been in place for many years. The metadata is made available for outside harvesting using this format and the OAI-PMH protocol.

Danish CRIS index

This component of the Research Portal Denmark (RPD) infrastructure harvests the institutional CRIS'es. The aggregated data is cleaned, normalized, enhanced, matched and clustered – and finally merged to produce the best possible one-publication-one-record index of the institutional data contributions. The Danish CRIS index makes its data freely available for downloading by others – and this is practiced by national as well as international entities.

OpenAlex indexing

OpenAlex downloads the data of the Danish CRIS index and integrates it in its global and open aggregation of research outputs (works). Apart from a global level repeat of the cleaning, normalizing, matching, clustering and merging efforts, this involves several data enhancements like adding Leiden-style topics and OECD Fields of Research and Development classification codes (FORD) to the records. Firstly, this contributes to a good coverage of Danish research in an open global database of growing importance. Secondly, these enhancements make the data interesting for RPD to harvest back and integrate in its database of Danish research outputs. This is done by downloading the monthly snapshots from OpenAlex and submitting the in-scope part of the data to the RPD ingest pipeline involving cleaning, normalizing, enhancing, matching, clustering and merging.

Adding CWTS Leiden indicators

High-integrity indicators known from the CWTS Leiden Ranking Open Edition are received from CWTS twice per year based on a list of in-scope OpenAlex works-ID supplied by RPD. In addition, CWTS delivers publication-level classifications of the subtopics defined in the Danish Green Research Strategy of the Ministry of Higher Education and Science. This enables RPD to offer these as a search criteria as well as to build analytical modules and dashboards that monitor research and innovation in connection with the green transition in Denmark. Finally, CWTS delivers global baseline and benchmark data for such analytical modules – as RPD only aggregates and indexes works-level data for Danish affiliated works.

Adding data from step 2-4 to Research Portal Denmark infrastructure

The open data from the Danish CRIS index, OpenAlex and CWTS are all submitted to the RPD ingest pipeline involving cleaning, normalizing, enhancing, matching, clustering and merging.

Adding licensed data to Research Portal Denmark infrastructure

In addition to the open data sources RPD also integrates licensed data from commercial providers. Currently these are Clarivate (Web of Science + Incites data), Digital Science (Dimensions data) and Elsevier (Scopus and SciVal data) – whether all of these will be part of the solution at the time of WOOC2025 remains to be seen. All this licensed data is also submitted to the RPD ingest pipeline involving cleaning, normalizing, enhancing, matching, clustering and merging.

Notifying Danish research institutions

Based on this wide-area aggregation and integration of data on Danish research, RPD has knowledge of works/publications that one or more sources consider as affiliated to a Danish

institution, which we did not find in the data coming from that institution itself. This enables RPD to notify the institutions about these potentially missing publications in their CRIS'es. Based on this, the institutions may choose to add the publication to their local system – copying data from the open part of RPD or drawing on their own commercial license agreements as they wish.

Search and analytics services of Research Portal Denmark

As already touched upon RPD offers a range of search services – currently for publications, patents, and grants with more to come – and a beginning range of analytical services – starting with module on Danish green research with many more to come. Whenever publication data is part of such a service it benefits from the international collaboration described above.

Conclusions

This presentation describes a virtuous circle gradually improving the coverage, openness, integrity and utility of a national research information infrastructure and portal. Currently under development with Summer of 2025 as the launch deadline, by the time of WOOC2025, the project will be able to report on what went well and what turned out to be more difficult than expected. All RPD software is open source and equipped with open documentation.